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Pastoral Counselling and Educational Development: Tools for Improving National Security in the 21st Century

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Abstract

This study investigates ways by which Pastoral Counseling and Educational development can improve national security. Pastoral counselling helps theological institutions grow and improve in ways to care for students and staff in a rather supportive way and this brings about the growth of the country. Pastoral counselling and educational development teach the counselling skills needed to improve national security skills to help churches and church leaders such as pastors and counsellors, to serve others better in different ways. Pastoral counseling develops counseling skills designed to enhance the ministry of the pastor in his relationship with the perceived counselee people to live in humility and obedience to the law of Nigeria. Survey research technique of data analysis was used in this study because of its effectiveness in attitudinal and behavioural studies. One hundred copies of the questionnaire were administered and recovered. The data was analyzed using frequency tables and simple percentages. The purpose, challenges, and importance of improving the performance of pastoral counsellors were discussed as well as recommendations. This article explores ways in which pastoral counselling reflects educational preferences and references to the Nigerian context. The theoretical framework used for this paper is "Reality Therapy". This study recommends that there is an urgent need for pastoral counseling to be introduced to the theological seminaries to help pastors in training to enable them to counsel their members very well because being a pastor is different from being a good counselor. This study concluded by saying, that when the pastor is equipped with pastoral counseling techniques, the counselee will get his/her desired answers which in turn foster peace in his life and vice-versa national development.

Keywords: Counsellor, Pastoral Counsellor, Development, Education

Introduction

Winkel (2005), defined counselling as a relationship between a professionally trained and competent officer and an individual seeking help in gaining greater self-understanding, improved decision making, and acquiring behavioural changing skills for problem resolution and development. Counselling unlike other professions, provides a safe place for clients or students to talk and process their thoughts feelings and needs.

It has been observed that most ethno-religious conflict broke out as a result of inciting statements either through religious sermons or publication by different religious groups (Ayinla, 2010). Counselling is a process in which the counsellor facilitates the expansion of

students' view of life enlarges the repertoire of coping resources and enables them to make appropriate choices (Yeo,1993)

In the Nigerian educational system, a Pastoral Counselling degree is to be designed for those who plan to pursue vocations in congregation-based ministry. It is to improve the student to serve a diverse community by facilitating healing and growth through reflectively integrating Christian values, principles, and resources of pastoral counselling practices with theological tenets and experience.

According to Abiri (1996), a society can only be considered desirable if it provides adequate guidance and counselling to help individuals, especially pastors, set realistic goals and reach their full potential, leading to effective ministerial development. Pastoral counseling is a unique form of psychotherapy that uses spiritual resources as well as psychological understanding for healing and growth. The educational industry is the bedrock of sustainable human capital development and progress in any nation. It is also globally recognized as an agent of positive change in all spheres of national endeavor. The success of the education industry depends largely on the level of professionalism, integrity, competency, and dedication of teachers who are the prime movers of the industry (Okesina, 2012).

Pastors can professionally discharge their task of facilitating meaningful learning by maintaining a very high level of academic development. Academic development is also an advancement in the educational pursuit of a pastoral counselor to help in moral uprightness, honesty, soundness, and unimpaired or uncorrupted condition (Barber, 1998).

Consequently, man as a social animal is a unit of sociological and spiritual studies, where he acquires his learning experience that sharpens his personality and aids in the process of physical and spiritual adjustments which pastoral counsellor suggests. Humans encounter multi-dimensional problems within living, ranging from social, environmental relational, mental, emotional, psychological, medical, educational, cultural, humanitarian, and personal. This shows how the educational development of pastoral counsellors affects these counselling practices because it enhances the affective, cognitive, and psychomotive domains of individuals in the past, present, and future life experiences.

Meanwhile, there are four phases of counselling vis; clarification, formulation, intervention, and termination. In this field, some principles are significant in bringing improvement, insight, effectiveness, exposure, growth, and changes that impact lives for good.

Purpose of the study

This study investigates the impact of pastoral counseling on national security, educational pursuit, development, and the perception of pastoral counsellors. It further aims to help pastors restore wholeness into people's lives, systems, relationships, and existence. Hence, intended pastors need pastoral counseling training in their programme in the seminaries.

Significance of the Study

For development to be achieved by counsellors, Gary Collins enumerated, the process of relationship that can be result-oriented between the pastoral counsellor and the counsellee, the process i.e.: attending, listening, responding, teaching and filtering. This will help counsellors

to be effective in bringing changes in peoples' lives using psychological and biblical-based counselling for future reasons.

In counselling relationships, the counsellor being cautious might incorporate theological facts to identify a problem, guide, educate, motivate, encourage and advise the counsellee towards living responsibly. Some of the theological facts include sin and salvation, guilt and forgiveness, despair and hope, love and hatred, anger, grace and redemption, and judgement and grace. There are stages of life that need the assistance of pastoral counsellors before one can make positive headway in life. The apostles took an assignment of counselling the converts in the bible.

Statement of the problem

Over the years, there have been developmental crises, most pastors have mixed up pastoring with pastoral counselling. Pastoral counselling is quite different from pastoring a congregation because it has its own techniques or skills of practices. Other root causes of pastoral emotional problems due to lack of educational-counselling development include over-reaction to events, conflict over inner expectation, over-identification, unresolved issues, sensitivity to failure, and the like.

Therefore, in the previous research reviewed, the Author elaborates on some importance that can help pastoral counsellors improve their performance in carrying out their duties (Owoade, 2022). Here, this study investigates pastoral counsellor perception of educational development and its impact on counsellors.

The pastor framed or equipped with pastoral counselling skills or techniques is best equipped to meet the immediate emotional, social, environmental relational, mental, emotional, psychological, medical, educational, cultural, humanitarian needs of his members or people around, unlike the pastors without the knowledge. This works with the scriptures and pastoral counselling theories, not leaving out pastoral matters. So, a pastoral counselling course should be introduced to seminaries, and theological and mission training institutions to enable pastors and missionaries to farewell in ministry.

Scope of the study

This study covers both the staff and pastors-in-training of the Redeemed Christian Bible College, main campus, Mowe, Ogun State, and as required the administration of the questionnaire.

Research questions

This study attempted to provide answers to the under-listed questions as a pathway to achieve the stated purpose of the study.

1. Does Pastoral Counselling improve the security of the nation?
2. Is there any relationship between educational development and Pastoral Counselling?
3. Does the intended Pastors need pastoral counseling in their theological training?

Methodology

The Redeemed Christian Bible College students were used for the study, this set of students have been workers in the church for years so they will be able to give adequate information in response to the questionnaire. The inability to expose student/pastors to pastoral counseling programme can be attributed to the teething problems of insecurity in churches today caused by pseudo-pastors. The survey research technique of data gathering and analysis was used because of its effectiveness in getting the current facts, opinions, motivations, and behavior of people.

The population of this study is limited to the ministers and pastors in training in the college's main campus because of the diversified nature brought to bear positively on the survey conducted. The qualitative and quantitative sampling method is the procedure adopted by the researcher in arriving at her sample size of 100 respondents given 100 questionnaires respectively in their various offices and classrooms.

Analysis

Subject responses were then subjected to descriptive statistical analysis using frequency tables and percentages to analyze the data.

Table 1-3 GENDER, AGE AND DESIGNATION DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESPONDENTS.

Table 1 As represented in the table below, most respondents are males, 90 in number, accounting for 90% of the total while the remaining 10% are females. It is safe perhaps to deduct from this simple frequency table that more males than females are ministers or pastors in the redeem Christian Bible College.

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
MALE	90	90%
FEMALE	10	10%
TOTAL	100	100%

Table 2 Age Distribution of Respondents

From the frequency table below, it is apparent that majority of the respondents are those in their thirties and forties, 10 people making 10% have their ages ranging between 19 and 29 respondents, which make 10% of the total, are aged between 51 and above. The age range with the most number of respondents is 30 to forty with 50 people making 50% half of the total, while those above the age of 41 and 50 are 30, amounting to 30%. It is clear from this analysis that not many people below 30years of age are ministers or pastors in the pastor.

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
19 ~29	10	10%
30~40	50	50%
41~50	30	30%
51~ABOVE	10	10%
TOTAL	100	100%

Table 3 Designation and Distribution of Respondents

From the table below, it is clear that majority of respondents are pastors, 70 in all making 70% of the total, while the remaining 30, accounting for 30% are ministers.

DESIGNATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
MINISTER	30	30%
PASTORS IN TRAINING	70	70%
TOTAL	100	100%

FIELD SURVEY 2023

Results on Evaluation of the Study

Table 1: For the purpose of this study, three research questions were formulated. These were further broken down to contingency nine items to further probe the respondents in proving answers to the formulated research questions based on rank or score-position of their responses YES or NO.

Item 1: The impact of Pastoral Counselling and Educational Development on cohesion and national security

Item 2: There is a relationship between educational development and pastoral counseling

Item 3: Intending pastors and ministers need pastoral counseling in their theological training

Item 4: There are differences between pastors and pastoral counselors prior to their educational development

Item 5: The national security and cohesion is dependence on the pastoral counseling training of ministers.

Item 6: Pastoral counseling training should be an effective capacity development tool for church in this nation.

Item 7: Ministers and lecturers in seminaries benefit from the pastoral counseling

Item 8: The educational development of pastoral counselors have effect on their performance

Item 9: The spiritual healthiness of the church is dependence on the pastoral counseling training of the minister.

Item 1: The impact of Pastoral Counselling and Educational Development on cohesion and national security

Table 2 Distribution of respondents on pastoral counselling

DESIGNATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
YES	90	90%
NO	10	10%
TOTAL	100	100%

This study result on table2, 90% of the respondents were of the affirmative response. Meaning that majority of the pastors and ministers accept that pastoral counseling helps the nation in peace and security, as presented in the table above.

Item 3: Impact of Pastoral Counselling techniques on National Security

Table 3 Distribution of respondents rating the relationship responses in yes and no

Relationship	Frequency	Percent
Yes	80	80%
No	20	20%

There is relationship between educational development and pastoral counseling, from the data generated from the table above. Out of the total of 100 respondent 80 agreed that there is relationship between the training which is an affirmative response which means those 20 pastors who said no have not attended the training and as not rated it to be fair.

Item 3 There is a Need for Intending Pastors in Nigeria to have pastoral counseling in theological training to help Nigerians growth

Table 4 Distribution of respondent's appreciation of the pastoral counseling training

COUNSELLOR TRAINING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
YES	88	88%
NO	12	12%
TOTAL	100	100%

From the data presented in the table above, 88 respondents in RCBC that has undergone the pastoral course appreciated it and others that are yet look forward to the experience. While 12 respondents says no because they have not attended the training and are still ignorant.

Discussion on the Result Findings and Implication

It is obvious that there is relationship in the pastoral counseling and educational development, the majority of the respondents indicated that pastoral training has effect on their performances as it was rated above average.

Pastoral training to a large extent has impact on the performance of pastors and ministers.so as to get prepared for the work ahead with necessary information and knowledge needed in their duty post.

Conclusion

Across the nation, more than 3000 pastoral counsellors provide a variety of services including treatment for persons with mental disorder; counselling for adults, adolescents, children, families and couples: substance abuse treatment, wellness programs, religious retreats, spiritual direction, clinical training, and consultations to corporations and outreach preventive services in prisons, community settings and schools. There is urgent need for educational development of pastors in training on pastoral counselling by including it into their course of programme in the Institution. If all Pastors or Missionaries undergo the pastoral counselling training in the context of principles and practices of guidance counsellor they will be fit to render their duties as a trained therapist not pseudo counsellor lacking the in-depth

knowledge of counselling and people will not blame them on any result of counselling sessions.

Nigeria at large will be peaceful, when the pastors and counsellors are well equipped to help the people with emotional, physical, social, environmental, relational, mental, emotional, psychological, medical, educational, cultural, humanitarian and spiritual concerns. Here vital issues that are interconnected with pastoral counsellors who have vast knowledge in doing eclectic method of counselling their various members as discussed and should be put into workable practices. As Solomon said in Ecclesiastes chapter 12; 13-14. "Let us hear the conclusion of the whole matter; fear God and keep His Commandments for this is the whole duty of man. For God will bring every work into judgement, including, every secret thing, whether good or evil".

Recommendation

1. Tertiary institutions should formulate curriculum inculcating the pastoral counselling trainings on biblical basis and theories of counselling.
2. Government should approve the establishment of pastoral counsellor offices outside the church settings to help people in need of professional pastoral counsellors.
3. Pastoral counsellors should improve themselves by attending refresher courses and trainings regularly for their own educational development.
4. There must be caring and counselling for marital relationship, caring and counselling during grief period, burnout and sustainable nature because the empirical view of the planet earth revealed that something dramatic need to be done quickly to redeem the collapsing status of nature and the environment.

References

- Alastair V. Cambell (ed.) 1987, p.198). *Dictionary Of Pastoral Care* (in this paper coted as DPC). The Crossroad publishing company, New York.
- American Association of pastoral counsellors. 2015, *History of Pastoral Counselling*.
- Counselling as a tool for promoting peaceful Co-existence in Nigeria. Counsellor Education: The Nigerian Journal of Guidance and Counselling University of Ilorin,78.
- Michael Jacobs, "Pastoral counselling and psychotherapy", in; David Willows and John Swinton ds.), spiritual Dimensions of pastoral care. Practical theology in a Multidisciplinary context, Jessica Kingsley Publishers, London, 2000, p.90.
- Owoade Abiodun 2022, The Importance of Making Available Pastoral Counselling as A Competence Course for Cross-Cultural Missionary Trainees, A conference Paper Presentation of Nigerian Association of Pastoral Counsellors: LCU, Ibadan, 2020.
- Stephen Ogundipe, Perspective on Caring and Counselling for Humans and Sustainable Nature: A Paper Reviewed in the Redeemed Christian Bible College, Ogun State, 2015.
- The Holy Bible, New International Version. Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1970
- Thomas C. Oden (1989, p.7). *Pastoral Counsel*. Crossroad, New York.